

Ἀντίοχος Θεὸς Ἐπιφανῆς.
Remarks and Suggestions about Antiochus IV's
Deification.

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1. Some preliminary remarks

Antiochus IV, called Epiphanes by his people¹ and Epimanes by his enemies,² was among the most powerful and ambitious Hellenistic kings.³ Many ancient authors have written about his deeds;⁴ numerous coins show his portrait and titles.⁵ Thus his reign is rather well documented,⁶ and we do not lack information about it. Nevertheless, we are often perplexed by the information we get from our sources. For example, there is an obvious contradiction between the abundant coins bearing the king's deified portrait and the accounts of ancient authors who tell nothing about his deification, but rather narrate stories that do not suit at all to a deified monarch. One may ask the following questions: Is it possible to reconcile Antiochus' divine monetary image with his unkingly behavior, which stunned the ancients? Was Antiochus, eventually, a self-deified king, as many scholars believe?

Hellenistic ruler cult is an exciting subject and has been extensively studied.⁷ In this context, two important points need to be kept in mind. First, ruler cult had a rather ambiguous nature.⁸ It operated simultaneously inside and outside of established religious traditions. Though heavily influenced by traditional beliefs and cults, it was also a kind of religious revolution.⁹ It had both religious and political character.¹⁰ It was not just a sign of civic servility but could provoke authentic religious sentiments.¹¹ Second, it was usually connected to civic environment. In the case of the Seleucids, barring two out of three letters of Antiochus III concerning the institution of his wife's cult,¹² the inscriptions that mention divine honors for the rulers or priests for the ruler cult come from cities, mostly of Asia Minor.

Why would a king tolerate, expect, promote, or even impose his cult upon his subjects? To force his presence even in their religious life¹³ or to legitimize his power, in the case he lacked legitimacy?¹⁴ Today, most scholars believe the latter. However, as it was rightly remarked in the past, royal legitimacy was obviously not a consequence of ruler cult or royal divinity, but the result of military power and heritage. Ruler cult was their result, not the inverse.¹⁵

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¹ App. Syr. 45.

² Pol. 26.1.1.

³ Mørkholm 1966, 13–17 and Mittag 2006, 11–17 for a summary of previous opinions on Antiochus. For their own judgement: Mørkholm 1966, 181–191 and Mittag 2006, 332–341; see also Will 1982, 306–308, and more recently Joannès 2014.

⁴ Mørkholm 1966, 17–20 and Mittag 2006, 18–31; Bernhardt 2017, 35–71, 166–168.

⁵ SC 2, 41–126.

⁶ However, almost no text — inscription or any other record — has come to us directly from him, except perhaps the beginning of a royal *πρόσταγμα* passed during his invasion of Egypt: P. Tebtunis III, 698. Jewish sources preserved some letters of Antiochus, but there are many problems concerning their authenticity and date: Habicht 1976; Bertrand 2006; Ma 2012.

⁷ In general: Chaniotis 2003, Aneziri-Buraselis 2004, Iossif-Chankowski-Lorber 2011 and Gnoli-Muccioli 2014; Iossif 2014 for the Seleucids.

⁸ Eloquently written by Bouché-Leclercq 1913/1914, 466 : “*Il y a dans tous ces hommages un certain flottement de la pensée et comme une équivoque voulue.*”

⁹ Van Nuffelen 1998/1999, 178–182, and 188.

¹⁰ This is widely accepted since the important study of Price 1984. The private dedications to kings and queens attest its religious character: Aneziri 2005.

¹¹ Price 1984, 17–40.

¹² Only the letter from Nehavend in Iran concerns a city, Laodicea in Media. See Canali de Rossi 2004, n.452–453 (Eriza), n.271–272 (Kermanshah) and n.277–278 (Nehavend), and Rougemont 2012, n.66 (Nehavend) and n.68 (Kermanshah) for the previous editions, and Iossif 2014, 140–146.

¹³ Virgilio 2003, 45.

¹⁴ For example, in the case of the Successors; see Anson 2014, and Hauben and Meuss 2014. For many, the development of the ruler cult in the early Hellenistic period relates to the legitimacy so much needed by these kings. See Iossif and Lorber 2009b, 32–33 and Anagnostou-Laoutides 2017, 149ff for the efforts specifically of the Seleucids to approach their Oriental subjects and to legitimize themselves in their eyes. For a different view: Erskine 2014. Walbank 1992, 217 rightly emphasized the role that the ruler cult played in the amelioration of the relations between kings and cities.

¹⁵ Bickerman 1938, 256–257 noted *inter alia*: “... *le monarque régnait ... non en sa qualité divine, mais en vertu de la victoire et du droit héréditaire... n'était qu'une conséquence de la puissance royale dans son fondement.*” Interesting, and to the point, is Adcock's statement reported by Walbank 1984, 99: “*Ruler-cult was not the root of Hellenistic monarchy: it was rather the leaves*

The aforementioned three letters of Antiochus III are our sole evidence for a centrally organized ruler cult in the Seleucid kingdom. Unfortunately, its precise nature and duration elude us totally. The rest of the evidence exclusively concerns ruler cult decided by civic authorities. Under Seleucus IV, an inscription from Seleucia in Pieria informs us about this kind of civic cult; it mentions two priests, one for the royal ancestors and another for the living monarch.¹⁶ Seleucus was bestowed unspecified divine honors at least at Seleucia, but similar civic cults probably existed elsewhere too. On the contrary, under this king, there is no evidence at all for a centrally organized ruler cult, by means of which the king could promote actively or even impose his divinity and cult throughout the kingdom.

The discussion about Antiochus IV and ruler cult is always influenced by suggestions about Antiochus' motivation. As he supposedly had several reasons to promote his cult, most believe that he certainly did it. Often, scholars connect his deification to the problems he had to face during his reign. Among them, three are mentioned frequently: First, his lack of legitimacy because of the circumstances of his rise to the throne; second, his humiliation and consequent loss of prestige at Eleusis; and third, a problem within the kingdom itself—its lack of unity.

Antiochus became king rather unexpectedly. After having been a hostage in Rome for several years, he was suddenly replaced by his brother's elder son and released. In Athens, he heard about his brother's death and set out for Syria with Attalid support.¹⁷ There, he found Laodice, his sister and Seleucus' wife, and Seleucus' very young son Antiochus.¹⁸ As some coins bear the legend "of King Antiochus" and the portrait of the child Antiochus alone or with his mother Laodice,¹⁹ it is safe to assume that the youngster was named king before his uncle's arrival in Syria. Probably a bit later, Antiochus IV married Laodice, adopted his nephew²⁰ and named him his coregent.²¹ The issues with the portrait of the child Antiochus stopped.²² Some

on the branch...". Walbank 1992, 96 described ruler cult as giving rather a luster to the royal dignity, while Walbank 1984, 86 noted that the treatises on kingship seemingly totally ignored the ruler cult and royal divinity.

¹⁶ OGIS 245.

¹⁷ Our evidence is: App. Syr. 45, an Athenian decree of 178/7 (IG II³, 1 1309), a copy of another Athenian decree of 175 from Pergamum (OGIS 248), and a cuneiform King List from Babylonia (BKL), first published by Sachs and Wiseman 1954, then by Del Monte 1997, 208–211, Glassner and Foster 2004, 134–135, and recently by van der Spek as "Babylonian King List of the Hellenistic Period" on the site of Livius. The BKL was not, of course, a purely historical text. His author did not verify the exact dates of the events; he noted them just as he heard them.

¹⁸ Mørkholm 1966, 43–50; Will 1982, 304–306; Mittag 2006, 42–48; Bunge 1974b, 57–60.

¹⁹ SC 1365–1372, Mørkholm 1964 and Le Rider 1986. According to Le Rider 1986, 416, the gold coins show that this coinage in the name of Antiochus the child antedated the issues in the name of Antiochus IV.

²⁰ Aymard 1953 and 1955, 109–112 wrongly thought that the child Antiochus was Epiphanes' natural son. The adoption of the youngster by his uncle was suggested by Mørkholm 1966, 46–47, who noted two errors of BKL: first, that Antiochus son of Seleucus became king and shortly afterwards associated his own son Antiochus on the throne; second, that he reigned for eleven years. Probably, the author of BKL heard only of Seleucus' death and the accession of his son Antiochus in the month of *Ululu* (Aug./Sept.), but he missed what happened in the capital at Epiphanes' arrival. Then, he learnt about the coregency of Antiochus (IV) and Antiochus his son (in fact, his nephew) in the month of *Arahsamnu* (Oct./Nov.).

²¹ Aymard 1953, 59.

²² Scolnic 2014 tried to rearrange the chronology of Epiphanes' initial years, as suggested by Mørkholm 1963, 34–37 and accepted by Le Rider 1999, 223–224 and SC 2, 41–44. Scolnic's criticism is not unjustifiable. The silver coins are undated and only a few bronzes bear dates, late in the reign. The chronology suggested by Mørkholm is very plausible, but not totally certain. The main problem with Scolnic's suggestion is that his numismatic assumptions are erroneous. Scolnic misunderstood SC 2, 37, ignored the numismatic bibliography, and did not have basic numismatic knowledge concerning coining dies and production. Accordingly, he concluded that the issues as well as the reign of the child Antiochus should have lasted down to 170 BCE. His suggestion is based on a single phrase about the volume of this king's coin issues in SC 2, 37, where one reads: "*The output of tetradrachms for the child Antiochus is surprisingly large for so brief a reign...*" Nevertheless, Epiphanes' coinage was much larger. Le Rider 1999 listed three obverse dies for tetradrachms for the child Antiochus, and fifty-seven for Epiphanes! For Antiochus V, whose reign lasted less than two years, Le Rider 1999, 234–247 listed twenty-one obverse dies for tetradrachms! Besides, the coins of the child Antiochus were struck only in three mints. More than ten mints issued silver coins for Epiphanes and six for Antiochus V. Scolnic's suggestion is not justified by the numismatic material; the coins clearly show that the reign of the child Antiochus was brief. Therefore, Scolnic's proposal that Epiphanes did not have full power before his nephew's death are solely based on the Book of Daniel (11, 21–24), whose interpretation is strenuous and problematic. Other literary sources probably give the answer: They almost exclusively mention Epiphanes—only the death of the youngster is rarely mentioned—and show him acting with full power.

years later, as the BKL narrates, Antiochus (IV) ordered the death of his “son”;²³ no documents mention the two kings any further.

Many scholars believe that Epiphanes was in so great difficulties in the beginning of his reign that he had to adopt his nephew; some of them also believe that he lacked legitimacy even after his nephew’s death in 170 BCE.²⁴ No doubt, Antiochus had to make compromises. Nonetheless, except for the Book of Daniel, no source, not even the hostile ones, mentions Antiochus’ lack of legitimacy.²⁵ Surprisingly, Antiochus’ cultic epithets appeared on coins probably after two years of reign, though, allegedly, he desperately needed some promotion. In my opinion, this problem seems over-emphasized. Other Macedonian kings had been found in similar situations, i.e., as guardians of young princes. Obviously, in the Macedonian monarchy, heritage was important, but often personality and conditions prevailed.²⁶ Furthermore, Epiphanes was not a stranger; he was a Seleucid, the son of Antiochus III, and he was strong enough to become king and not just the guardian of his nephew.

Antiochus’ war against Egypt and the Roman intervention at Eleusis resulted in new difficulties. Usually, the “Day of Eleusis” is considered to have caused so much trouble for the king that he soon sought ways to regain his lost prestige.²⁷ However, this view of “Eleusis” as a great disaster seems exaggerated.²⁸ In my opinion, it even offered the king an exit from the impasse. During his first expedition, Antiochus had failed to seize Alexandria though he had with him Ptolemy VI²⁹. It would have been more difficult for him to capture it against the will of the reconciled Ptolemies. Did he lose part of his prestige? Certainly. But he also defeated the Egyptians, plundered Egypt, and came back with a rich booty. In addition, he reconfirmed his rights over Coele-Syria. Would this victory be forgotten so soon? Probably not.

Similarly, one should be critical of the claim that Epiphanes, as well as every Seleucid, promoted his cult to enforce unity in the realm.³⁰ This view, sometimes linked to theories about Antiochus’ alleged Hellenizing projects, seems anachronistic. Did the Seleucids ever try to impose unity? Did they do it by imposing the ruler cult?³¹ Probably not. Their model was not Macedon with its high demographic homogeneity, but rather the Persian Empire, and other Near Eastern empires that came before it, whose peoples also lived together under

²³ According to van der Spek’s translation: “10 The same month: An(tiochus), his son, ascended the throne. He reigned for eleven years. 11 The sam[e year], (in the month) Arahsamnu An(tiochus) and An(tiochus), his son, [were] kings. 12 [Year 1]42, (in the month) Abu, at the command of An(tiochus), the king, An(tiochus), the king, his son, was killed. 13 Year 143, An(tiochus IV was sole) king.”

²⁴ All the articles of Bunge (1973, 1974a, 1974b, 1975, 1976, 1979) are based on the idea of the illegitimacy of Epiphanes’ rule. According to Bunge, Antiochus had to promote actively his disputable legitimacy even after his nephew’s death. Earlier, Bevan 1902, 127–128 and Abel 1941, 246 also believed that Antiochus sought to stabilize his power for many years. Hoover 2002b, 85 considered that Antiochus IV married his sister and even employed her portrait on bronze coins (SC 1407 and 1477) to legitimize his own position. Wright 2012, 66 considered his marriage with Laodice and the adoption of his nephew as a compromise with a similar aim. In contrast, Paltiel 1979, 44–47 suggested a rather heretical view: Antiochus was so strong that he even had good relations with Demetrius, Seleucus’ legitimate heir.

²⁵ Scolnic 2014 proposed a new interpretation of *Daniel* 11, 21–24. He suggested that it reports, in a cryptic way, the assassination of the child Antiochus. This is, however, far from certain.

²⁶ Buraselis 2017 on cases of *epitropeia*, mostly in Macedon (Philip II, Antigonos Doseon, etc.), and on the rather easy passage from the *epitropeia* to the throne thanks to the guardian’s relationship with the ruling dynasty, the existing notions about kingship, and the state difficulties.

²⁷ Mørkholm 1966, 95–96. Gruen 1993, 355–357 explained Antiochus’ violent intervention in Judea as his attempt to publicly display his might and to offset “Eleusis.” Bernhardt 2017, 211–215 described “Eleusis” as the bitterest humiliation for the king, almost a circumcision. Antiochus’ most successful attempt to regain his prestige would be the great festival at Daphne: Mørkholm 1966, 97–101; Mittag 2006, 282–295; Bunge 1976; Walbank 2002, 85–89; Iossif 2011; Erskine 2013; Brisson 2018; Strootman 2019.

²⁸ I agree with Morgan 1990, 71–72 and his answer to Gruen in Gruen 1993, 264–269; more recently Mittag 2014, 131–133. Earlier, Otto 1934, 82–88, esp.84 and Tarn 1938/1951², 192 crossed their swords on the meaning of “Eleusis.” Otto considered it a disaster that affected Antiochus personally, while Tarn praised the king’s calm reaction.

²⁹ Tite-Live 45.11.

³⁰ La Rocca 1994, 21.

³¹ Hannestad-Potts 1990, 122–123 noted the absence of a unified religious architecture in the Seleucid kingdom. Apparently, no Seleucid policy of unification ever existed.

a foreign ruler.³² Obviously, the Achaemenids never promoted unity through the imposition of their cult.³³ Furthermore, Antiochus did not have to face these problems any more than his Seleucid ancestors or his royal neighbors did.

2. The numismatic evidence

In comparison with the coins of his predecessors, Epiphanes' coins are different in manifold aspects. In fact, some serious monetary reforms took place during his reign. Among those, two are extremely important: the reduction of the weight of the tetradrachms in Antioch and Ptolemais, and the introduction of new bronze denominations in several mints.³⁴ Other changes concern external aspects of the coinage, e.g., the royal portrait, the reverse types, and the legend; these are the most significant evidence for Antiochus' deification. I shall start from the most "eloquent messengers" on the coins—the images.³⁵

2a. The portrait

“οἱ δὲ προσήνεγκαν αὐτῷ δηνάριον. καὶ λέγει αὐτοῖς: τίνας ἢ εἰκῶν αὕτη καὶ ἡ ἐπιγραφή; λέγουσιν Καίσαρος.” Matt. 22.20–21.

The above evangelical quote is very interesting; it shows that during the first century AD, people in Palestine could recognize the portrait and the titles of the emperor on the coins.³⁶ Subjects of the Hellenistic kings could probably do the same. Coins were certainly the most obvious means for rulers to make their faces, names, and royal dignity known throughout their realms. Although other means existed, e.g., statues and portraits could be sent to the cities,³⁷ only the coins could be found everywhere.

The monetary portrait of the Seleucids had an interesting evolution.³⁸ Under Seleucus I, the administration probably refrained from putting the king's portrait on the coins.³⁹ This changed later, when under Antiochus I, his portrait—and occasionally his deified father's portrait—was put on the coins issued in his name.⁴⁰ Afterwards, most Seleucid coins bore the royal portrait.⁴¹ These portraits show the way the administration allowed the mint authorities to depict the king, so that sentiments of devotion be provoked among subjects. We do not know if these images were loyal to their prototype; every royal portrait was idealized and aimed at providing a positive image of the ruler.⁴²

Epiphanes' monetary portrait attracted much attention. Its study is, however, difficult, since the silver coins bore no dates; only a few bronze coins do.⁴³ Nevertheless, the studies on some mints enable us to follow with some certainty the evolution of the portrait in them. The lack of dates, however, does not allow for chronological comparison with other mints. This is a great obstacle to deepening our understanding of the king's portrait.

³² Since the eighties, the scholars sought the continuities and the ruptures between the Achaemenids and the Seleucids: Briant 1990 and Panitschek 2016.

³³ On the question whether the Achaemenids ever enjoyed ruler cult: Rollinger 2011, Root 2013, Wiesehöfer 2014.

³⁴ On the weight reduction in Antioch: Mørkholm 1963, 38–43, and 54; Mørkholm 1982, 304–305; Mørkholm 1984, 106–109; Schlösser 1986; Le Rider 1999, 225–226; Mittag 2006, 123–127; Doyen 2014, 266–268; at Ptolemais: Voulgaridis 2000, 46–47. On the introduction of new bronze denominations in Antioch and elsewhere: Le Rider 1994 and 1998; Doyen 2014, 271–276.

³⁵ Images were intelligible to almost everybody. Svenson 1995 on the display of the Hellenistic kings as gods is extremely helpful.

³⁶ For the context: Finney 1993, 629–633.

³⁷ Vandegeerde 1984, 59–69.

³⁸ Smith 1988, 13–14, and 45; Fleischer 1991 and *SC* under each reign.

³⁹ For the identification of persons—and horses—on Seleucus I's coins: Hadley 1974 and Houghton-Stewart 1999, who refused to recognize Seleucus, while Babelon 1890, xv, Newell 1978, 181, and recently Hoover 2002a, Iossif 2004 and Erickson 2013 suggested the opposite. In *SC* 1, 6–7, the authors do not make a final choice.

⁴⁰ *SC* 1, 114–115.

⁴¹ Under Antiochus Hierax, there were coins with recognizable portraits of Antiochus I and Antiochus II; it is not certain we have a monetary portrait of Hierax himself. See *SC* 1, 293–294.

⁴² Smith 1988, 45–46; Sheedy 2007, 11–12.

⁴³ Rare royal bronzes (*SC* 1461) and some municipal ones (*SC* 1441, 1463–4, 1466, 1494).

Before we examine Epiphanes' rejuvenated portrait, two other aspects —the *anastole* and the inclination of the royal head— should be briefly mentioned, as both attracted some attention and led to appealing suggestions. *Anastole*, the hairstyle of Alexander the Great,⁴⁴ which was reminiscent of a lion's mane and accordingly of a lion's courage and strength, is occasionally found on Epiphanes' portraits. Sometimes, it has been interpreted as a sign of *imitatio Alexandri*,⁴⁵ although it never became a regular feature of the portraits. In the monetary mints of Antioch and Ptolemais, where the *anastole* is usually found, only some rejuvenated portraits bear it.⁴⁶ Probably, it was nothing more than an artistic choice.

The case of the inclination of the head is more problematic. It was first noted by Mørkholm, who remarked that on some coins of Antioch, the king was shown "*leaning forward in a most awkward way.*"⁴⁷ Mørkholm considered that this could not be the artist's intention and suggested in the plates he prepared the way the coins were meant to show the king. The result was a portrait of Antiochus gazing into the heavens.⁴⁸ Mørkholm interpreted this upwards inclination as "*an outer sign of the divinely-inspired ruler.*" This suggestion is reasonable; it would be in Antiochus' interests to demonstrate his piety towards the heavens.⁴⁹ However, Mørkholm had to change the actual axis of the coins, as if they were systematically incorrect. Moreover, as this inclination concerns only some coining dies, there is much room for doubt about Mørkholm's suggestion.⁵⁰

When he ascended to the throne, Antiochus was a man in his early forties.⁵¹ Like his father —as he grew older— and his brother —also in his forties— Antiochus probably had receding hair over his temples. This is what we see on his so-considered more realistic monetary portraits (Pl.1, 1).⁵² However, some mints — sometimes from the beginning of their issues— used a different kind of portrait, showing a much younger person with rich hair, often long, occasionally with *anastole*. It was not the first time that coins presented an idealized and slightly younger portrait of a Seleucid king;⁵³ this time, however, the differences were many. The rejuvenated royal portraits of Epiphanes do not remind much of the realistic portraits from Ptolemais. A quick comparison between these realistic portraits and the rejuvenated ones from the same mint is surprising (Pl.1, 2). It is not only the denser and longer hair; the head is often bigger, the jaw, the nose, and the eye are larger and of distinct shape, too. These could be portraits of different persons with little or even no resemblance to the king.

What was the meaning of this idealized and youthful royal portrait? Why was Antiochus depicted so much younger? From an anthropological perspective, his youth could be symbolic, probably an instrument of nature's fertility.⁵⁴ Nevertheless, its sudden appearance under Epiphanes and the silence of our sources incite not to adopt this perspective. That is why this rejuvenation was considered as evidence of deification. According to Bunge, Antiochus promoted his self-deification for reasons of propaganda and to cure his lack of legitimacy. The rejuvenated portrait of Antiochus would aim precisely at his aggrandizement in the detriment of the child Antiochus, his coregent and Seleucus IV's legitimate heir.⁵⁵ It would promote Epiphanes through his godlike image, showing his divine qualities, youth and beauty. The authors of *SC* saw also an

⁴⁴ L'Orange 1947, 3; Smith 1988, 47; Fleischer 1991, 45; Stewart 1993, 76–77. Of course, an *anastole* is found also on the depictions of Helios.

⁴⁵ There is an allusion in Mørkholm 1963, 62. Ehling 2008, 86 connected it with Antiochus' oriental expedition.

⁴⁶ The dies A32–A45 of Antioch and A4, A6–A7, and A10–A11 of Ptolemais in Mørkholm 1963.

⁴⁷ Mørkholm 1963, 61.

⁴⁸ Mørkholm was influenced by L'Orange, who wrote a whole chapter about "*Heavenward-gazing Alexander*" (1947, 19–28). Also, Smith 1988, 47.

⁴⁹ *SC* 2, 46.

⁵⁰ Already, Fleischer 1991, 49–50.

⁵¹ Mørkholm 1966, 38; Mittag 2006, 33–34 and n.5.

⁵² The dies A1 and A2 from Ptolemais in Mørkholm 1963 (*SC* 1472–1474).

⁵³ E.g., under Antiochus I: *SC* I 311, and 318. For the aspect of youthfulness of many royal portraits: Smith 1988, 46–47. Usually, the king's age on the coins is adapted to the circumstances.

⁵⁴ On this aspect of kingship: Quigley 2005, 9 with mention to Frazer's ideas.

⁵⁵ Bunge 1975, 165.

evolution from human to godlike portrait; in Mørkholm's words, Antiochus' rejuvenated portraits were those "of a god or hero, separated from mankind in timeless youthfulness."⁵⁶

Let us now examine more closely Epiphanes' portrait on his silver coins⁵⁷ throughout the kingdom.⁵⁸ In Antioch, from the beginning,⁵⁹ we find a rather idealized portrait with some personal features. The king is shown certainly younger, yet he is recognizable. A change occurred in *ca.* 173/2 BCE⁶⁰ when the portrait became more idealized and youthful, with longer and denser hair, and devoid of personal features. Despite the indisputable influence of Antioch⁶¹, this portrait evolution did not become normative everywhere. At Tarsus, some rather realistic portraits with a recognizable Antiochus were followed by clearly idealized ones. In the small mints of Seleucia on the Calycadnus and of Soli, there were only rather realistic portraits. At Ptolemais, the second-ranked mint in importance, the issues started later;⁶² unexpectedly, the two first dies bore what seem to be the most realistic portraits of Antiochus.⁶³ The artists at Ptolemais had certainly seen not only the first rather idealized portraits from Antioch, but also the new ones after 173/2 BCE. A similar realistic portrait, but of lesser artistic quality, was employed in another western mint, probably Seleucia in Pieria.⁶⁴ A while later, the mint at Ptolemais adopted an idealized portrait, youthful and devoid of personal characteristics (Pl.1, 2). In the East, the mint of Seleucia on the Tigris used rather realistic portraits with many personal traits of Antiochus, but there were also some rather idealized ones. At Susa, the portrait was idealized, and the king is barely recognizable. At "Antioch in the Persian Gulf", the portrait is rather realistic. At Ecbatana, the situation is complicated: rather realistic portraits, which sometimes show an older version of the king (Pl.1, 3), are interchanged with rather idealized ones, often with few personal traits. Among the mints of uncertain attribution, in the one that issued "tetradrachms with draped bust and star(s)" and in the other that issued tetradrachms and drachms with a radiate portrait, the portraits are rather realistic. At Antioch in Persis, and Uncertain Mint 80 the portraits were rather idealized.

Apparently, nothing indicates that the idealized portrait was promoted, since it is not found everywhere. Clearly, the king did not impose it. Furthermore, at Antioch and Ptolemais, the first issues were quite limited and at Ptolemais rather late.⁶⁵ It is strange for a king allegedly desiring to promote himself and his legitimacy to not issue more coins at the beginning of his reign. This was, however, the case of the very short-lived coinage in the name of the child Antiochus.⁶⁶ In this context, many questions arise: Why did the mint at Ptolemais start its issues with a realistic royal portrait? Why did other Western and chiefly Eastern mints never adopt the new idealized portrait? Why was there no special attempt to combine the divine traits, youth, and beauty with the personal traits of the king? Why did all this happen first under Antiochus IV?

⁵⁶ SC 2, 46; Mørkholm 1963, 58.

⁵⁷ The portraits on bronze coins are not especially useful in this discussion. In most cases, they show a radiate portrait, are small, and not very well preserved; it is not always easy to discern which type of portrait –realistic or idealized– they bear. We find, however, both types, the latter probably more often.

⁵⁸ Table 1. I assume that the two first portraits at Ptolemais (A1–A2) are the more realistic ones. My classification results from the comparison to those portraits and is, obviously, subjective.

⁵⁹ According to Mørkholm 1963, 9–11 and 34–37, the first silver issues date a bit after Antiochus became king.

⁶⁰ Mørkholm 1963, 34–37.

⁶¹ Mørkholm 1963, 52.

⁶² Around 170. See Mørkholm 1963, 52–53 and Voulgaridis 2000, 40–42.

⁶³ On these portraits: Fleischer 1991, 48; Mørkholm 1963, 62.

⁶⁴ This attribution, suggested by Mørkholm 1965/1966, 9–11, seems very probable.

⁶⁵ Mørkholm 1963, 34–37, 52–53.

⁶⁶ SC 1368–1371 (Antioch) and SC 2, 37–38.

2b. Divine attributes

“...καὶ τὸν μικρῶ πρότερον τῶν οὐρανίων ἀστρῶν ἄπτεσθαι δοκοῦντα παρακομίζειν οὐδεὶς ἐδύνατο διὰ τὸ τῆς ὀσμῆς ἀφόρητον βάρος.” 2 Macc. 9.10.

The rejuvenated royal portrait was not the only iconographic innovation that displayed Antiochus’ deification. Other elements —star-like symbols and rays— were even more explicit. Regarding them, two preliminary remarks are necessary: First, they were not employed throughout the kingdom; second, they were not always or exclusively linked with idealized portraits. Some realistic or rather realistic portraits were also decorated with stars or rays.⁶⁷

The stars were an innovation of Epiphanes’ reign. Though their use was limited geographically, they have “haunted” every scholar interested in Antiochus IV,⁶⁸ since the most prolific Seleucid mints, Antioch and Ptolemais, employed them to decorate the royal portrait. The stars are found mostly on silver coins; only a few bronzes show Antiochus with a star over the diadem. A single star over the diadem is also found on the earliest silver tetradrachms of Ptolemais (Pl.1, 1), and on the rare ones attributed to Seleucia in Pieria and to the Eastern mint of “tetradrachms with draped bust and star(s)”. In Antioch, after a few early issues without stars, two stars decorated the extremities of the diadem.⁶⁹ Later, this disposition was adopted by the mint at Ptolemais as well (Pl.1, 2). Eventually, this mint conformed to the fashion from Antioch.⁷⁰

Rays were more frequent.⁷¹ They are found mostly on bronze coins, royal and municipal ones⁷² (Pl.1, 4). Rarely, they are also found on silver coins: on small denominations of Antioch and on the full coinage of an Eastern mint⁷³ (Pl.1, 5). Interestingly, stars and rays were never used together.⁷⁴ They were obviously interchangeable and surely had the same meaning. But why were the stars used more often on silver coins, like the tetradrachms, whereas the rays mostly on bronzes, which were smaller? The cause could be their size. Perhaps, it was thought that the stars would not be clearly visible on small-sized coins.⁷⁵

What was the meaning of these stars and rays? What was their message?⁷⁶ Generally, they are considered signs of Antiochus’ divinity. Two theories are advanced within this frame of reference: They are explained either literally, namely as celestial symbols, stars and solar rays, or as symbols of a divine light.⁷⁷ In an

⁶⁷ Table 2.

⁶⁸ Babelon 1890, xciii, and Cerfaux and Tondriau 1957, 244 n.1 connected 2 Macc. 9.10 with the earliest tetradrachms from Ptolemais showing a star above Antiochus’ head (SC 1472). However, as Abel 1949, 399–400 —but not Starcky in Abel-Starcky 1961, 65 and 276a—, Bartlett 1973, 288 and Doran 2012, 188–189 rightly noted, 2 Macc. 9.10 describes rather the fall of an arrogant man. The exaggerations imputed to Antiochus have biblical parallels, e.g., Isa. 14, 13–15.

⁶⁹ The first issues (SC 1395) bore no stars. Later, the stars seem tightly linked to the diadem and often appear to be attached to it. Could they be a decoration of the diadem, as supposed Le Rider and de Callatay 2006, 47 n.3? The Ptolemies decorated their diadems this way: Kyrieleis 1986, 57 and Fleischer 1991, 46.

⁷⁰ A rather strange choice, since the stars on the extremities of the diadem were certainly less visible. On most coins, this part of the die is out of the flan. The tetradrachms showing the one or both stars are rare.

⁷¹ Antiochus’ radiate portrait is also found on Mesopotamian seals: Rostovtzeff 1932, 28.8 (pl.V, 1) and 44.67 (pl.V, 2).

⁷² The latter date between ca. 169/8–164: Mørkholm 1965. Not every royal bronze coin or every municipal one bears Antiochus’ radiate portrait.

⁷³ These coins of the mint of the “Silver coinage with radiate portrait”, of the mint of the “Tetradrachms with draped bust and star(s)” and a few others were attributed to an Antioch on the Persian Gulf by Mørkholm 1970, 31–34. This attribution was first refuted in SC 1517–1525 and more recently in Iossif and Lorber 2009a, 135–139.

⁷⁴ This happened later, under Antiochus VI (SC 2010.4), but in that case the star was rather the symbol of a magistrate.

⁷⁵ Mittag 2006, 135–136. Bunge 1975, 172 and Fleischer 1991, 48 advanced another theory. Outside his realm, Antiochus was called just Ἐπιφανής —meaning illustrious; inside, he was Θεός Ἐπιφανής, a clear sign of his deification. Similarly, the large silver coins, destined mostly to the international commerce, bore stars, considered less suggestive of royal *apotheosis*, while the bronze coins destined to local circulation bore rays, a clear symbol of *apotheosis*. One may, however, object firstly that there is no clear reason why the king or the mint staff should not use divine attributes on coins destined for the far-going commerce, and secondly that the tetradrachms bore the clearest evidence of royal *apotheosis*, the legend ΘΕΟΥ ΕΠΙΦΑΝΟΥΣ. Obviously, there was nothing to dissimulate. See also Iossif and Lorber 2009a, 140 n.73.

⁷⁶ Kyrieleis 1986, 58 rightly stated that the symbols should be easily comprehensible. Otherwise, they would fail their mission. For the meaning of the divine attributes on Hellenistic coins, see Iossif 2018.

⁷⁷ If the two stars were representations of real jewels, then these jewels should be considered either celestial symbols or signs of a divine light.

instructive article, Kyrieleis rightly noted the similarity between the single star over Antiochus' head and the one over the heads of each of the Dioscuri.⁷⁸ He showed also that this single star, over the gods or the king, should be viewed not as an astral symbol (a star or the Sun) but rather as a sign of divinity —as a divine light. Kyrieleis also evoked the popular belief in the Dioscuri as helper and savior gods manifesting in the need of the believers, mostly in the sea, bringing the calm and the first light of the stars or the sun after the storm. This does not necessarily mean that Antiochus was assimilated to the Dioscuri.⁷⁹ Rather, the way the Dioscuri were commonly depicted was employed to present the king with their qualities, those of a helper and manifesting divinity. The star-like symbol in both forms —a single star or two stars— could be then a sign of divinity, a sort of divine light that comes out from the deities, showing the king as a super-human being belonging to the divine sphere.⁸⁰ This is an appealing approach, one I fully adhere to.⁸¹

There is yet another minor problem concerning the stars. Why did the mint at Ptolemais eventually decide to discard the single star and to conform to the mode coming from Antioch? Was this just a question of fashion? Then, why did this mint not use this disposition from the beginning of the issues? The issues from Antioch antedate the first ones of Ptolemais by some years. There is no easy answer.⁸² It seems as if there was a kind of iconographic correction, as if the depiction of the king with a single star was not correct. Was this correction necessary to avoid a clear identification of the king with the Dioscuri? This does not seem improbable.⁸³

The rays pose almost the same problems. They also point to a possible identification of the king with Helios, whose iconography is imitated.⁸⁴ Interestingly, rays are also found on Ptolemaic coins. Some gold coins of Ptolemy IV show a radiate portrait of his deified father Ptolemy III on the obverse and a radiate *cornucopia* bound with royal diadem on the reverse.⁸⁵ Under Ptolemy V, there was one more innovation. Some gold coins show a radiate portrait of the living king.⁸⁶ Probably, these Ptolemaic issues influenced the depiction of Antiochus IV with a radiate crown, though there were some differences⁸⁷. Anyway, Epiphanes was the first Seleucid to be depicted in this way.⁸⁸ His first radiate portraits came from Antioch.⁸⁹ From there, they reached many other regions —to the Southern Levant, the Mesopotamia, and the Persian Gulf.

Stars and rays apparently had the same meaning. Therefore, the radiate crown does not mean that Antiochus was depicted as Helios and identified with this god; it might have been the equivalent of the divine light.⁹⁰ Of

⁷⁸ Kyrieleis 1986, 58 and 59 with images of the Dioscuri.

⁷⁹ Not least because the Dioscuri were two.

⁸⁰ Kyrieleis 1986, 61–62; Smith 1988.

⁸¹ For this metaphorical approach to the divine attributes: Iossif 2018, 272. Bunge 1975, 187 tried unconvincingly to connect stars and royal foundations. Antioch, Seleucia in Pieria, and Seleucia on the Tigris were founded by Seleucus I. Tyre was not a royal foundation either. For other cities, there are either problems of attribution or problems concerning their alleged (re)foundation by Epiphanes. For the problems concerning Antiochus' foundations or re-foundations: Mørholm 1966, 116–118 and Mittag 2006, 202–208, both criticizing Tcherikover 1927, 176.

⁸² To note that the coins from Ptolemais present some more stylistic differences in comparison to those from Antioch.

⁸³ Interestingly, three out of four identified mints that used a single star were certainly in cities with a port: Ptolemais, Tyre, and Seleucia on the Tigris.

⁸⁴ E.g., the Hellenistic coinage of Rhodes, for which see Ashton 2001.

⁸⁵ Svoronos 1117.

⁸⁶ Svoronos 1254. Iossif and Lorber 2012, 200–206 remarked that the rays were always fourteen and not of equal size.

⁸⁷ The remark made above does not concern Epiphanes' rays. Iossif and Lorber 2012, 207–208 rightly noted that the Seleucid imitation of the Ptolemaic radiate crown was rather superficial.

⁸⁸ Messina 2001 suggested that a Babylonian seal with a radiate portrait, reminiscent of Seleucus IV, was depicting young Seleucus as a prince. Nevertheless, as there is no sign of royal authority, the seal probably depicts the Sun. See Svenson 1995, 23.

⁸⁹ The radiate crown appeared in Antioch first on small silver denominations (*SC* 1405–1406) and on a new series of bronze coins (*SC* 1408–1411). As all bear an extended legend, they date after the first years of the reign, probably in *ca.* 173/2–169 BCE. A bit later, some coins of the so-called Egyptianizing series, of *ca.* 169/8 BCE, also bore a radiate portrait (*SC* 1415), as did the abundant series of the municipal coins (*SC* 1416–1418).

⁹⁰ Smith 1988, 42; Fleischer 1991, 46; Svenson 1995, 21. Bergmann 1998, 64–65 noted an interesting innovation in Ptolemaic Egypt concerning the hieroglyphics: the word God was replaced by a star. On Seleucid coins, no god except Helios ever bore a radiate crown. Obviously, the gods were effortlessly recognized. The radiate crown would be used to note a divinity otherwise not easily noticed.

course, there is no reason to deny the solar character of the radiate crown. Obviously, this well-known symbol was used in a new context—the imagery of the ruler and his cult—and the ruler certainly benefited from it.⁹¹

Wright put forward an interesting theory about the meaning of the radiate crown and suggested that behind Granius Licinianus' story (28.5) about the marriage of Antiochus to the goddess *Diana* at Hierapolis-Bambyce—in fact, the king seized the wealth of her sanctuary—is hidden an important religious event, a ritual sacred marriage. The radiate crown could, then, be the sign of the king's deification through his marriage with the goddess.⁹² Nevertheless, this theory finds no support.⁹³ More recently, Iossif suggested another approach to the royal divine attributes: They were gifts of the gods to the kings and, therefore, expressions of divine favor and of royal piety.⁹⁴

Some other iconographic elements should also be briefly mentioned. Recently, in connection to the king's deification, some discussion took place on a star over Apollo's head on some Eastern coins,⁹⁵ a sun-bust alongside Apollo on some coins of Seleucia on the Tigris,⁹⁶ and the apparition of a new iconographic type, of a goddess Nikephoros, on some bronzes.⁹⁷ Concerning the star and the Helios' bust, first Bergmann and then Iossif and Lorber assumed that they were linked to Antiochus' deification.⁹⁸ Although this is not improbable, the corpus that Mørkholm prepared for the mint of "Antioch on the Persian Gulf" clearly shows that this star was not constantly found on the coins in Antiochus' name. It can be found only on one reverse die (P1); there were at least three more showing no star over Apollo's head (P2-P4). The star on P1 could really have a special meaning and many suggestions can be made in this regard. Nevertheless, it cannot be classified alongside the other divine attributes, constantly found on the coins. Similarly, only some coins bear Helios' bust, not all. One can even doubt that this symbol has any connection with Antiochus' deification. Its mere presence cannot suffice.

The case of the goddess Nikephoros is more interesting. The apparition of this specific reverse type in a Western and three Eastern mints is remarkable. Iossif and Lorber discussed all available textual and iconographic evidence in an article on the Seleucid queens named Laodice, and suggested that this goddess could be Aphrodite, with whom Laodice, either the mother or the wife and sister of Antiochus IV, could have been identified.⁹⁹ This hypothesis is not to discard, but it cannot be of some use here, as there is no explicit evidence for the existence of a cult for the queen under Antiochus IV.

⁹¹ On the link between the kingship and the sun: Anagnostou-Laoutides 2012, 2. Bunge 1975, 167–168 noted that the use of the attributes of a known god was somewhat revolutionary and based on conscious decision. Solar symbols were well-known to Greeks and Orientals, and solar theology was already advanced and meaningful. Iossif and Lorber 2009b, 28–29 reminded that solar images were already known in the East and concluded that solar imagery could have been a unifying factor in the kingdom. See also Zolotnikova 2002, 247 about the solar nature of the universal god with whom Antiochus was allegedly identified.

⁹² Wright 2012, 61–64. Mørkholm 1966, 132 also recognized a ritual sacred marriage. Taylor 2014, 234–235 had a different view. A similar story about another sacred marriage of Antiochus IV is told in 2 Macc. 1.14, in the second introductory letter, in the context of the death of the king in Persis. There, the female deity is called Nanaia.

⁹³ This is a difficult information to treat. Besides, some numismatic remarks of Wright are not always tenable. Wright 2012, 62–63 noted that the radiate crown was used by one king at a time, that it was found only on coins of Epiphanes' descendants, and that Demetrius' family used it only after the extinction of Epiphanes' branch. Nevertheless, Demetrius Soter was depicted with rays at least twice (*SC* 1697 and 1703). Further, there were probably radiate portraits of two rival kings: Alexander II (*SC* 2233–2235 and 2237, *ca.* 125–122), and Antiochus VIII, a descendant of Demetrius I (*SC* 2274, 126/5 and later).

⁹⁴ Iossif 2018, 272 and 285–286. This is an interesting suggestion. Later, under Antiochus VIII, also an Epiphanes, the reverse of the king's earliest tetradrachms shows a Zeus having a crescent moon over the head and a large star-like celestial body in his extended right hand (*SC* 2297). Flipping over a tetradrachm of this type, one would see the god "offering" the star of epiphany to the king. See Iossif and Lorber 2009a, 140 note 72. However, some questions arise regarding Antiochus IV: Why are these gifts not seen everywhere? Which god offered them to the king?

⁹⁵ *SC* 1517–1518.

⁹⁶ *SC* 1505.2–3.

⁹⁷ *SC* 1508–1511 (Seleucia on the Tigris), 1512–1515 (probably Seleucia on the Tigris), 1533 (Susa), 1489–1490 (Samaria) and 1491 (probably Samaria). On one occasion (*SC* 1515) the goddess probably bore a star above the head.

⁹⁸ Bergmann 1998, 65 and Iossif and Lorber 2009a, 141.

⁹⁹ Iossif and Lorber 2007 *passim* and 87–88 for the conclusions. One may read, in the same context, Hoover 2002b.

2c. The cultic epithets

“Ἀντίοχος ὁ Ἐπιφανῆς μὲν κληθεῖς, Ἐπιμανῆς δ’ ἐκ τῶν πράξεων ὀνομασθεῖς...” Pol. 26.1.

There is yet another innovation on some coins in the name of Antiochus IV. Beside the simple legend, namely ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ ΑΝΤΙΟΧΟΥ (BA), one can read on them up to three extra epithets in different combinations: ΘΕΟΥ ΕΠΙΦΑΝΟΥΣ ΝΙΚΗΦΟΡΟΥ (ΘΕΝ). Apart from an enigmatic coinage with the legend ΣΩΤΗΡΟΣ ΑΝΤΙΟΧΟΥ,¹⁰⁰ the Seleucid mints started to inscribe royal cultic epithets on the coins first under Antiochus IV. Nevertheless, cultic epithets were used for the kings even before Epiphanes. These are known to us through the literary tradition¹⁰¹ and some inscriptions.¹⁰²

The remark made above about the rejuvenated portrait and the divine attributes applies to the cultic epithets as well: there was no uniformity regarding their use throughout the kingdom.¹⁰³ Only few mints employed them and often, in a different way. The mint in Antioch was the first that put cultic epithets on its coins. After some silver issues with BA, a new series appeared around 173/2 BCE bearing a legend with two extra epithets: BAΘΕ. For some years, this was the legend in use (Pl.1, 4). After Antiochus’ victorious first expedition against Egypt around 169/8 BCE, the epithet ΝΙΚΗΦΟΡΟΥ was added: BAΘΕΝ.¹⁰⁴ Regarding the bronzes, some bore the legend BAΘΕ, while the rest had the simple legend, or a municipal one.

Only at Ptolemais, we remark a similar evolution. After some issues in *ca.* 170–168 BCE with BA (Pl.1, 1), the new series bore BAΘΕΝ (Pl.1, 2). No coin with BAΘΕ is known from Ptolemais.¹⁰⁵ There was, however, yet another difference: at Ptolemais, no bronze coin bore a more extended legend, BAΘΕ or BAΘΕΝ, though the bronzes with a radiate royal portrait date certainly beyond 173/2 BCE.

In the western part of the kingdom, no other mint put an extended legend on its coins except some unknown eastern Syrian mints that issued bronzes with the legend BAΘΕ. In the East, there were some bronzes probably of Seleucia on the Tigris with the legend BAΘΕ, and some silver coins from Ecbatana with the legends BAΘ (Pl.1, 3) or BAΘΕ. Therefore, few mints used the new legend. Further, at Ptolemais, an issue in the name of Antiochus the son of Epiphanes —probably as coregent of his father— bore no additional epithets.¹⁰⁶ This is not surprising; coregents had no cultic epithets.¹⁰⁷ Unfortunately, as most coins under Epiphanes are undated, we cannot compare the evolution of the legend in different mints. It seems, however, certain that there was no clear pattern of evolution throughout the kingdom.¹⁰⁸

The cultic epithets on the coins were one of the legacies of Epiphanes’ reign. Under Antiochus V, five mints —Antioch, Ptolemais Tarsus, Byblos and Uncertain Mint 81— put this king’s cultic epithet ΕΥΠΙΑΤΩΡ on the coins in his name. Under Demetrius I, some mints added the epithet ΣΩΤΗΡ to the simple legend, and from the reign of Alexander I Balas, one finds cultic epithets almost everywhere.¹⁰⁹ Alexander I Balas claimed to be Epiphanes’ son. His usual cultic epithets on the coins were ΘΕΟΠΙΑΤΩΡ ΕΥΕΡΓΕΤΗΣ, the former

¹⁰⁰ SC 640–642. It is rightly considered posthumous, which explains the epithet ΣΩΤΗΡ alongside the king’s name. Nevertheless, many other mysteries about it remain.

¹⁰¹ Muccioli 2013; van Nuffelen 2009.

¹⁰² OGIS 233 (from Antioch in Persis under Antiochus III) and OGIS 245 (from Seleucia in the Pieria under Seleucus IV). OGIS 246 (from Teos) dates after Epiphanes’ death.

¹⁰³ Elsewhere too: de Callatay and Lorber 2011, 417–420. For the Seleucids: Bickerman 1938, 236–246 and de Callatay and Lorber 2011, 427–428. *Pace* Bickerman, de Callatay and Lorber consider that the epithets reflected the official will of the kings.

¹⁰⁴ Table 3. For the monetary legend in Antioch: Mørkholm 1963, 34–37 and 68–74, Mittag 2006, 128–133, and SC 2, 49.

¹⁰⁵ Mørkholm 1963, 50; Voulgaridis 2000, 40–43; Voulgaridis, *forthcoming*.

¹⁰⁶ SC 1581.

¹⁰⁷ Muccioli 2013, 124. Though Antiochus III is sometimes mentioned with his epithet Μέγας, his son and coregent Antiochus is always mentioned as Antiochus the son. See, for example, Robert and Robert 1983, n.14–15.

¹⁰⁸ Iossif and Lorber 2009a, 130 noted the diffusion of these epithets mostly in the West and ascribed it to the greater levels of (Greek) literacy in that region. How could one, however, explain that no additional epithets were used at some western cities, e.g., Tarsus? Bunge 1975, 181 thought that these epithets —other indices of royal deification as well— were related to Antiochus’ travels. Nonetheless, cultic epithets are occasionally found in Seleucia on the Tigris and in Ecbatana, where Antiochus probably never was. See Iossif and Lorber 2009a, 130.

¹⁰⁹ The most notable exception were the Phoenician weight issues of the Phoenician cities.

referring to Epiphanes. Furthermore, there are some posthumous coins in the name of Antiochus IV from those years. The earliest are bronzes from Apamea, struck in 151/150 BCE and bearing the simple legend. Five years later, however, other posthumous issues from Antioch —some dated to 146/5 BCE— bore the extended legend BAE.¹¹⁰

In the literary sources, Antiochus' name is occasionally followed by his principal cultic epithet, Epiphanes.¹¹¹ Neither Θεός nor Νικηφόρος ever appeared in literary texts; however, there is one exception: a petition of the “Sidonians of Shechem” to Epiphanes reported by Josephus. It is followed by a royal letter to Nicanor.¹¹² Although their authenticity is much debated,¹¹³ undeniably, both letters respect the forms of this kind of correspondence. Interestingly, the “Sidonians of Shechem” addressed their petition to the “King Antiochus God Epiphanes.” Their letter dates after the king's Egyptian expeditions, but curiously Antiochus' third epithet Nikephoros is absent. Remarkably, in the beginning of his answer to Nicanor, Antiochus gives himself no epithet at all; he uses only the royal title.¹¹⁴

Unfortunately, we have no letters of Epiphanes inscribed on stone. On the contrary, many letters of Antiochus III are preserved.¹¹⁵ A glance at them reveals that the king always presented himself as King Antiochus, without his cultic epithet Μέγας. Interestingly, even Zeuxis, the royal appointee in Asia Minor, in his letters to various cities, mentions his king only with his royal title.¹¹⁶

Epithets of Antiochus IV are also found in three inscriptions, all private. The first one mentions the epithets ΘΕΟΣ ΕΠΙΦΑΝΗΣ and some secondary ones. Two other inscriptions add to the royal title only the epithet ΕΠΙΦΑΝΗΣ.¹¹⁷ Finally, there is also the evidence from a weight of Syrian provenance with the legend ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ ΑΝΤΙΟΧΟΥ ΘΕΟΥ ΕΠΙΦΑΝΟΥΣ.¹¹⁸

What is the meaning of these cultic epithets? Like the divine attributes, these epithets were recognized as means of royal propaganda, and many linked them to Epiphanes' alleged lack of legitimacy.¹¹⁹ Among these epithets, Θεός was not really an innovation, as the Milesians gave this epithet to Antiochus II many decades

¹¹⁰ SC 1883–1884, 1885–1887. There is a notable difference with Soter's coinage: on the posthumous coins in Epiphanes' name the royal title is preserved!

¹¹¹ E.g., Jos. AJ 13.35. The use of royal epithets in historical texts became frequent after Polybius: van Nuffelen 2009, 96–107. Often, the use of this epithet concerns the introductory mention of the king. In later authors, name and epithets are more often used together, which supports van Nuffelen's opinion that later historians had king lists.

¹¹² Jos. AJ 12.258–261 and 12.262–264.

¹¹³ Bickerman 1937, 376–407; Bertrand 2006; Pummer 2009, 161–178; Bernhardt 2017, 231–235.

¹¹⁴ The simple form of the royal self-presentation was always employed —before and after Antiochus IV—, whenever a Seleucid king writes to his administrators. This is significant. Bickerman 1938, 255 thought that the centrally organized ruler cult —like the one organized by Antiochus III— was addressed to the Friends and the Court, and in general to people connected more to the dynasty and to the king than to a region and its gods. However, the fact that no king ever tried to manifest his divinity through his letters addressed to his officials seems to contradict this opinion.

¹¹⁵ See the rich epigraphic dossier in Ma 2002.

¹¹⁶ There are a few exceptions. In the inscription OGIS 746 from Xanthos, one reads: “Βασιλεύς Μέγας Ἀντίοχος ἀφιέρωσεν τὴν πόλιν...” Robert and Robert 1983, 164 showed, however, that this inscription was the product not of the royal chancellery, but rather a summary of the royal decision made by the Xanthians. In another inscription from Mylasa (Robert and Robert 1983, 186), there is probably the epithet Μέγας in a letter of Zeuxis. The phrase belongs to the reconstitutions of the text; perhaps one should try another suggestion. In the inscription of Hefzibah, the king is mentioned with his cultic epithet μέγας in the beginning of the second petition of Ptolemy: “21[βασ]ιλῆϊ μεγάλῳ[ι] Ἀντιόχῳ ὑπόμνημα...”, but not in the first one. The later Seleucids, in the few letters we know of them, do not present themselves with their known epithets. They always chose the simple form of legend. Similarly, in the cuneiform tablets: Wright 2012, 53.

¹¹⁷ The first is OGIS 253 of non-precise Mesopotamian provenance: “βασιλεύοντος Ἀντιόχου θ[εοῦ] Ἐπιφανοῦς || σωτήρος τῆς Ἀσίας καὶ κτίσ[του] καὶ ἐνεργέτου || τῆς πόλεως.” See Sherwin-White and Kuhrt 1993, 157, Boffo 1994 n.11, and Muccioli 2006. The two other inscriptions are dedications of the Milesian brothers Timarchus and Heracleides (Milet I 2, 1–2). Both mention: “...[ὑπὲρ] βασ[ι]λέως [Ἀν]τιόχ[ο]ν Ἐπ[ι]φ[αν]οῦς...” (Milet I 2, 1).

¹¹⁸ Babelon and Blanchet 1895, 679 n°2245 and Pondera online n°3591 with full references and photos. Perhaps, it dates after 169; it is decorated with a Nike, probably evoking Antiochus' Egyptian victories. Finkielsztejn 2012, 152 rightly remarked that these weights were part of clearly local activities and had no link with the central administration. Thus, this evidence —the private inscriptions too— do not probably concern our subject.

¹¹⁹ Bunge 1974b, 68.

ago.¹²⁰ Undeniably, this epithet is more than explicit and clearly puts the king into the divine sphere. Much discussion has also been made about Antiochus' identification with known gods. Nevertheless, as no god is explicitly mentioned in the legend, the king was obviously seen as a god of his own.¹²¹

Some interesting evidence dates beyond Antiochus' death. Antiochus V took the epithet ΕΥΠΑΤΩΡ just after his father's death.¹²² It is interesting to compare this epithet, which means the one who has a good father, with the epithet ΘΕΟΠΑΤΩΡ, taken some years later by Alexander I Balas, Epiphanes' alleged son.¹²³ *Theopator* could mean either one who has a god for a father or one who deified his own father.¹²⁴ One could ask, why did Antiochus V become just *Eupator* and not *Theopator*? Why did the posthumous issues in the name of Antiochus IV bear the legends ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ ΑΝΤΙΟΧΟΥ or ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ ΑΝΤΙΟΧΟΥ ΕΠΙΦΑΝΟΥΣ without ΘΕΟΥ?¹²⁵

No Seleucid king had ever used the epithet ΕΠΙΦΑΝΗΣ before Antiochus IV,¹²⁶ but it was employed a few decades earlier in the Ptolemaic kingdom. Ptolemy V (204–181) was the first Hellenistic ruler to bear it on coins¹²⁷, which were certainly in circulation in Coele-Syria and Phoenicia at the beginning of the Seleucid domination. Under Ptolemy V, one also notes a certain promotion of the ruler cult.¹²⁸ Probably, developments in Egypt exerted some influence on the Seleucid kingdom.¹²⁹ Of course, the notion of epiphany was always important in Greek religion¹³⁰. Everybody knew ancient stories about divine apparitions and interventions; some new were added in Hellenistic times.¹³¹ For the rulers, such an epithet would have evoked the manifestation of their power—mostly of military power and benefaction—resulting in striking events.¹³²

For Epiphanes, Appian narrates the dramatic events behind this epithet: After Seleucus IV fell victim of a conspiracy, Antiochus appeared and saved the kingdom.¹³³ This passage is in the heart of the most important questions about the Hellenistic royal epithets: At what moment were they given to the kings? Were they the result of a top-to-bottom decision or that of *vox populi*?¹³⁴ For Antiochus V, we have two different versions: Appian points clearly to *vox populi*, whereas the text of 1 Macc. as well as Josephus points to a decision of the Court, namely of the tutor Lysias.¹³⁵ In both cases, the kings took an epithet in the beginning of their reign

¹²⁰ Muccioli 2013, 290.

¹²¹ Nock 1928, 40 and Bunge 1974b, 82–83. Zolotnikova 2002, 252 saw Antiochus as the earthly embodiment—obviously through his epithet Epiphanes—of a universal deity.

¹²² Apart from the occurrences of this epithet in the literary sources, e.g. 2 Macc.10.10, there is also the inscription SEG 41.1556, a petition to the king from the “Sidonians at Jamneia”, reporting a letter of Antiochus V, self-presented as βασιλεὺς Ἀντίοχος, to a Seleucid official. In the beginning of the petition one reads: “βασιλεῖ Ἰ Αντιόχοι Εὐπάτορι...” Of importance is also the information from Jos. AJ 12.361: “Λυσίας δὲ τὸν θάνατον αὐτοῦ δηλώσας τῷ πλήθει τὸν υἱὸν αὐτοῦ Ἀντίοχον, αὐτὸς γὰρ εἶχεν τὴν ἐπιμέλειαν, ἀποδείκνυσι βασιλέα καλέσας αὐτὸν Εὐπάτορα.” Josephus follows 1 Macc. 6.17.

¹²³ SC 2, 213.

¹²⁴ Both suggested in Muccioli 2013, 297.

¹²⁵ ΘΕΟΣ is also found on Svoronos 1486 from Ptolemais, a coin in the name of Ptolemy VI..

¹²⁶ Several will after him. De Callataÿ and Lorber 2011, 450 (index) and 439–442 (kings).

¹²⁷ These coins are rare. Lorber 2006, 15–16 mentions a few tetradrachms (Svoronos 1249), probably from the province of Syria and Phoenicia, and some Tyrian bronzes. On ΕΠΙΦΑΝΗΣ as cultic epithet of Ptolemy V: Nock 1928, 38–41; Bunge 1974b, 68; Hazzard 1995; Lorber 2006; Muccioli 2013, 285–287.

¹²⁸ Hazzard 1995, 419–421, 428 for the context and Johnson 2002 on the important inscription OGIS 98.

¹²⁹ As had also the events in the beginning of Ptolemy VI's reign: Bunge 1974b, 72. The Ptolemaic influence over the Seleucid kingdom was certainly strong at that moment: rays, epithets, Egyptian monetary types.

¹³⁰ Versnel 1987; Platt 2015.

¹³¹ E.g. Paus. 10.23.3 about Apollo's miraculous intervention at Delphi against the Celts.

¹³² The Ithyphallic hymn in the honor of Demetrius Poliorcetes describes such an epiphany. See Chaniotis 2011, 173–176 and Nock 1928, 40.

¹³³ App. Syr. 45: “ὁ μὲν Σέλευκος ἐξ ἐπιβουλῆς Ἡλιοδώρου τινὸς τῶν περὶ τὴν αὐλὴν ἀποθνήσκει... Οὕτω μὲν Ἀντίοχος ὁ Ἀντιόχου τοῦ μεγάλου Συρίας ἐπεκράτησεν· ὅτω παρὰ τῶν Σύρον ἐπώνυμον ἦν ἐπιφανῆς, ὅτι τῆς ἀρχῆς ἀρπαζομένης ὑπὸ ἀλλοτρίων βασιλεῶν οἰκεῖος ὄφθη.” Appian is the only source reporting the assassination of Seleucus by Heliodorus.

¹³⁴ Muccioli 2001. One should not forget in this context an earlier case from the third century: Antiochus II, called Θεός by the Milesians. This is also reported by App. Syr. 65.

¹³⁵ Appian Syr. 46, “...Ἀντίοχον, ᾧ προσέθησαν ὄνομα Εὐπάτωρ οἱ Σύροι διὰ τὴν τοῦ πατρὸς ἀρετήν.” In 1 Macc. 6.17 one reads: “καὶ ἐπέγνω Λυσίας ὅτι τέθνηκεν ὁ βασιλεὺς, καὶ κατέστησεν βασιλεύειν Ἀντίοχον τὸν υἱὸν αὐτοῦ, ὃν ἐξέθρεψεν νεώτερον, καὶ ἐκάλεσεν τὸ ὄνομα αὐτοῦ Εὐπάτωρ.”

—in the case of Antiochus V, without even a notable action by the king, who was a minor. Later, Demetrius I took the epithet Soter after having defeated Timarchus in Mesopotamia —another case of *vox populi*, reported again by Appian.¹³⁶

It is not surprising that many doubts have been thrown over Appian's evidence.¹³⁷ However, without Appian's information, we are in the dark. In the case of Antiochus IV, the event linked by Appian to the epithet *Epiphanes* is certainly very well chosen. An objection, namely that this epithet appeared on the coins in *ca.* 173/2, with a delay of almost two years, seems unconvincing. No Seleucid before Antiochus ever saw his cultic epithets on the coins. It was an innovation; this delay is rather natural. Of course, as the years passed, the epithet *Epiphanes* was more linked with the royal person and the royal actions, and manifested more durable, general qualities of the king.¹³⁸

The epithet *Nikephoros* attracted less attention. In the past, it was used to support the idea of Antiochus' identification with Zeus.¹³⁹ However, Mørkholm refuted this claim, as there are some coins from Ptolemais with Apollo on the omphalos and the extended legend BAΘEN.¹⁴⁰ Obviously, there was nothing connecting Zeus Nikephoros and the epithet *Nikephoros* of Antiochus. In fact, *Nikephoros* is obviously related to Antiochus' victory over Ptolemaic Egypt. Moreover, Mørkholm thought it was meant to reestablish the royal prestige after "Eleusis." However, it is not known when exactly this epithet was first used on the coins. Probably, this happened either after the first or the second Egyptian expedition of Antiochus. I think, we need not to see a means to efface a defeat, mostly because there was no defeat: it was certainly a great victory over Egypt, even if it was followed by the Roman intervention. The main problem with *Nikephoros* is again its limited use. Why is its use limited in Antioch and Ptolemais?¹⁴¹

In most literary, historical, and epigraphical texts, Antiochus is mentioned only with his epithet *Epiphanes*. According to Fleischer and Bunge, this was the result of a royal policy about the use of the royal cultic epithets.¹⁴² According to them, outside the kingdom Antiochus promoted only his epithet *Epiphanes*; this epithet creates a certain ambiguity, as it also means illustrious. The epithet *Theos*, which was more explicit about his divine nature, as well as the epithet *Nikephoros*, had a limited use, inside the kingdom. Nevertheless, we should acknowledge that no cultic epithet appears everywhere in the kingdom. Besides, the tetradrachms bearing these epithets were coins that could travel and carry their messages to the West. The evidence on which the above suggestion is based is epigraphic, namely the dedications of the Milesians brothers Timarchus and Heracleides.¹⁴³ There, the royal name is followed only by the epithet *Epiphanes* probably since there is also a reference to the god of the place, Apollo of Didyma.

¹³⁶ Appian *Syr.* 47. One should also consider the role that the elites or the Court played in these events. Both could easily influence the people.

¹³⁷ Nock 1928, 41; Brodersen 1989, 63; Van Nuffelen 2009, 102. On the contrary, Bickerman accepted this information and suggested that the royal epithets could be the result of *vox populi*. For Bickerman 1938, 237–242, this could explain the differences of the titles inscribed on the coins; a view with which I agree.

¹³⁸ Mittag 2006, 128–130.

¹³⁹ Bevan 1902, 155; Abel 1941, 246.

¹⁴⁰ *SC* 1475.

¹⁴¹ Zolotnikova 1997 made an interesting connection with the goddess Nikephoros on some bronze coins, but her hypothesis seems going too far.

¹⁴² See above n.75.

¹⁴³ See above n.117.

3. Literary sources

“Ὅτι Ἀντίοχος προσφάτως παρειληφώς τὴν βασιλείαν ἐνεστήσατο βίον παράλογον καὶ ἀσυνήθη τοῖς ἄλλοις βασιλεῦσι.” Diod. 29.32.1.

The scanty epigraphic evidence is already discussed above; let us now turn to the literary sources. A great deal of information and many ideas about Antiochus IV come from Jewish texts. Among them two are particularly interesting for our subject: the second book of the Maccabees and the Book of Daniel.

In 2 Macc., Antiochus is often portrayed as an irascible¹⁴⁴ and exceedingly arrogant person. He allegedly thinks he is capable of what only (the) god(s) can do, namely commanding nature.¹⁴⁵ 2 Macc. 9.12, which presents a statement allegedly made by Antiochus himself in his illness,¹⁴⁶ poses more problems.¹⁴⁷ Many supposed that this was a clear allusion to Antiochus’ self-deification, presented as true by the author, who thus put Antiochus into a long tradition of arrogant kings who thought themselves as gods.¹⁴⁸ Nonetheless, it is unclear whether the king also believed he was godlike.¹⁴⁹

The evidence of the Book of Daniel is much more enigmatic.¹⁵⁰ The *ex eventu* prophecies interweave with past tradition and probably with real prophecies about the end of times. It is difficult to know which parts are information about the past and which are prophecies. In ch.11, there is a summary of Hellenistic history down to Epiphanes’ reign, which focuses on the relations between Egypt and Syria. Using a cryptic language, the author gives information that his readers would probably recognize as true. People of that time, but also of later times, probably recognized, correctly or falsely, persons and situations. *Daniel* heartened them in the troubles they lived in. This makes an apocalyptic text interesting for generations after its writing. Of course,

¹⁴⁴ 4.38: “καὶ πυρωθεὶς τοῖς θυμοῖς...”; 5.11, “...τεθριωμένος τῇ ψυχῇ...”; 9.4, “ἐπαρθεὶς δὲ τῷ θυμῷ....”

¹⁴⁵ 5.21: “...οἰόμενος ἀπὸ τῆς ὑπερηφανίας τὴν μὲν γῆν πλωτὴν καὶ τὸ πέλαγος πορευτὸν θέσθαι διὰ τὸν μετεωρισμὸν τῆς καρδίας” and 9.8, “...δοκῶν τοῖς τῆς θαλάσσης κύμασιν ἐπιτάσσειν διὰ τὴν ὑπὲρ ἄνθρωπον ἀλαζονεῖαν καὶ πλάστιγγι τὰ τῶν ὀρέων οἰόμενος ὕψη στήσειν...” These citations are often linked with biblical passages, where divine power over the nature is described (Is. 40.12 and 51.15; Job 38.11; Ps. 65.8, 89.10, 106.9; Nah. 1.4), but also with Herodotus’ story about Xerxes’ arrogance and *hybris*, where the Persian king tried to impose his will upon the sea in the Hellespont and upon the land at Athos peninsula (Her. 7.22–24, 33–36 and Aesch. Persians 744–751). For a discussion: Abel 1949, 355 and 399–400; Abel-Starcky 1961, 254 and 276; Habicht 1976, 227 and 245; Goldstein 1983, 260–261 and 354; Schwartz 2008, 263 and 357; Doran 2012, 131–2 and 188–9. I have already discussed 2 Macc. 9.10, above n.68. Compare also with Her. 3.30 relating Cambyses’ dream about his brother Smerdis: “ἔδοξε οἱ ἄγγελον ἐλθόντα ἐκ Περσέων ἀγγέλλειν ὡς ἐν τῷ θρόνῳ τῷ βασιλιῷ ἰζόμενος Σμέρδης τῇ κεφαλῇ τοῦ οὐρανοῦ ψάσσειε.”

¹⁴⁶ “Δίκαιον ὑποτάσσεσθαι τῷ θεῷ καὶ μὴ θνητὸν ὄντα ἰσόθεα φρονεῖν.”

¹⁴⁷ There is also a problem concerning the manuscripts: Abel 1949, 401 and Schwartz 2008, 358–359. However, the choice of *ισόθεα* seems correct.

¹⁴⁸ Schwartz 2008, 359 noted as biblical background Is.14.13–14 on the arrogant Babylonian king. Abel 1949, 401 and Goldstein 1983, 355 added some passages from Greek drama (Aesch. Persians 820 and Soph. Trachniae 472–3). For the formation of 2 Macc. 9.12: Schwartz 2007, 262–265.

¹⁴⁹ A brief mention should be made to 2 Macc. 6.7: “...ἤγοντο δὲ μετὰ πικρᾶς ἀνάγκης εἰς τὴν κατὰ μῆνα τοῦ βασιλέως γενέθλιον ἡμέραν ἐπὶ σπλαγχνισμὸν...” The Jews were compelled to participate in monthly sacrifices on Antiochus’ birthday and to eat from the offered meat. These sacrifices, which were usual in Hellenistic period, were probably not connected to a centrally organized ruler cult. See Doran 2012, 137, mostly Vanderkam 1981, 61–68, and van Henten 2007, 273–274, who preferred to ascribe this reference in 2 Macc. to a Ptolemaic context.

¹⁵⁰ There are many questions regarding *Daniel*; the most significant concerns its date. Even if a Maccabean date is widely accepted today, some support also exists for a much earlier date: Ferch 1983. The discussion in Koch 1980: 8–12 and *passim*, who accepted a Maccabean date, helps to realize the great difficulties in the interpretation of this text. Recently, Wildgruber 2013 strongly criticized the historical-critical exegesis of *Daniel* 11, and rightly exposed serious cautions against the use of it as a pure historical text. *Daniel*’s theological-apocalyptic character is often sacrificed, when it is viewed as a historical text, and this seems to be a major problem. Moreover, *Daniel* is not a historical treatise. His author did not try to give accurate historical knowledge. He aimed to comfort the persecuted Jews. In this context, historical information aimed mostly at supporting the prophecy about the end of the persecution, of the king, and of the world itself. The apocalyptic nature of the text does not imply that everything said about the past or the present is certainly true; it is rather the view its author had about the past or can even be his propaganda. Besides, this text depends heavily on a long tradition, which makes its date more difficult to ascertain than it seems. Many parts of *Daniel*, while usually interpreted as alluding Hellenistic events, can also be read within the context of older biblical prophecies. On the Book of Daniel, see Koch 1980, Delcor 1993, and Collins 1993, but also Blasius 2004, 78–88, with much information about its reading in antiquity and in modern times.

this happens in a way consistent with the long Jewish literary tradition. There is, however, reason for worry. How certain are we that Antiochus is not presented in a typified way?¹⁵¹

In *Daniel*, the phrases 11.36–38 are most interesting.¹⁵² Before 11.36, the author relates events of the first decades of the second century; 11.39 concerns Antiochus' policy towards his partisans. From 11.40, the author recounts a new clash between the Northern and the Southern kingdoms, namely the Seleucids and the Ptolemies. As this new round of conflict never took place after the intervention of the *Kittim*-Romans at Eleusis, we have a prophecy. Verses 11.36–38 do not relate events; they describe the religious behavior of the Northern king.¹⁵³ In 11.36, it is precisely written that “...*the king will do as he wishes...*” Does this have any historical value at all?¹⁵⁴ Almost the same phrase is used for the Persian Empire (8.4), then for Alexander the Great (11.3) and Antiochus III (11.16). This was a typical way to describe tyrannical behavior.¹⁵⁵ No surprise there; nothing would stop a king at the peak of his power. Soon, the reader expects that this cannot continue for long. In the case of Alexander and Antiochus III, their end is described in the verses that follow. For Antiochus IV, this is expected to happen the way it is prophesied in the verses after 11.39.

More interesting is the double reference that “36... [*the king*] will exalt and magnify himself against every god ... 37... for he will magnify himself against all.” Does this prove that the king promoted his self-deification?¹⁵⁶ This was Bevan's opinion,¹⁵⁷ who was probably the first to interpret these verses in this way and to use the numismatic evidence as support.¹⁵⁸ Other commentators before Bevan had, however, interpreted this excerpt differently.¹⁵⁹ Certainly, this vocabulary is usually applied to God (compare with Is. 30.10), but it is also used in contexts where arrogance is reprimanded in a metaphorical language.¹⁶⁰ Nevertheless, Bevan's prestige and his use of the numismatic evidence, rather than the evidence itself, influenced the research. Many commentators followed Bevan's suggestion, though his ideas about Epiphanes' coinage were refuted some years later.¹⁶¹ In my opinion, the phrases in question seem to describe, in a rather typified way, one more, arrogant foreign ruler. Besides, one should not forget that what is written in *Daniel* is not necessarily true; it is the view that a Jewish group in Palestine, or elsewhere, had about Antiochus and his actions against Jewish religion and the Temple.¹⁶²

To sum up, as Collins put it, these verses are polemical.¹⁶³ I would add that, even if there was some historical information in them, it is probably rather exaggerated. The purpose of the description of Antiochus

¹⁵¹ Lebram 1975 is important; he offered new, surprising insights suggesting that there was significant Egyptian influence on *Daniel* (p.761–765), as well as influence from the Herodotean story of Cambyses (p.765–771 and his conclusion p.771–772). On the Herodotean influence, see also Niskanen 2004; it is true, there are many similarities between Danielic Antiochus and Herodotean Cambyses. See also the conclusion of Delcor 1993, 385–386 and the discussion in Honigman 2014, 70–73. For the tight link of *Daniel* with the Jewish Scriptures: Clifford 1975–1976, 25 and Henze 2012, 291–299.

¹⁵² Here is the translation from Hebrew by Collins 1993, 368 “36/ *The king will do as he wishes and will exalt and magnify himself against every god, and he will speak wondrous things against the God of gods, and he will succeed until the wrath is finished, for that which is decreed will happen. 37/ He will not attend to the gods of his fathers, even to the [god] beloved of women he will not attend, for he will magnify himself against all. 38/ He will honor the god of strongholds instead; a god whom his fathers did not know he will honor with gold and silver and precious stone and costly things.*”

¹⁵³ Everybody –except those supporting an earlier date for *Daniel*– recognized Antiochus IV: Goldingay 1989, 304; Hartman-Di Lella 1978, 301; Collins 1993, 386.

¹⁵⁴ On the historical value of the information about Antiochus' behavior: Delcor 1993 *passim* and 385–386. Also, Clifford 1975–1976, 93–94, who rightly noted that in 11.36–12.3 the author of *Daniel* drew upon older traditions.

¹⁵⁵ Goldingay 1989, 304; Hartman-Di Lella 1978, 301; Collins 1993, 386.

¹⁵⁶ Aperghis 2011, 74 rightly remarked that Antiochus is seeking his self-deification only in *Daniel*. In his opinion, these verses belong rather to the prophetic part and have no historical value at all. See already, Millar 1997, 102.

¹⁵⁷ In more detail in Bevan 1900, and then in Bevan 1902 II:155.

¹⁵⁸ Babelon 1890, xcii–xciv had already seen Antiochus as a Hellenizer presenting himself as god on his coins.

¹⁵⁹ E.g., Bevan (Anthony Ashley) 1892, 195–196, who noted the contradiction between *Daniel* 11.36–37 and the information given by non-Jewish authors.

¹⁶⁰ Is. 10.15 is characteristic; it speaks of an object, a saw, “*exalting itself above him who wields it.*”

¹⁶¹ Goldingay 1989, 304 and Hartman-Di Lella 1978, 301. On the contrary, Collins 1993, 387 accepted Mørkholm's objections and the evidence of the festival at Daphne, where Antiochus showed his reverence towards the gods.

¹⁶² Already Will-Orrieux 1986, 113.

¹⁶³ Collins 1993, 387–388.

as a tyrant was obviously to show the root of the evil: the villainous character of the foreign king.¹⁶⁴ According to *Daniel* 11.37–38, the king was so evil that he did not attend his own ancestral gods and worshiped a new god instead, unknown to his fathers.¹⁶⁵ In the context of antiquity, where *πάτρια* had a great value, while *νεωτερίζειν* was wicked, the behavior ascribed to Antiochus was certainly reproachable.¹⁶⁶ What good could one expect from a king of this kind?

Jerome's commentary on *Daniel* is also of great interest. In his commentary, Jerome often discussed the polemical opinions of Porphyrius, the Neoplatonist philosopher of the third-century CE. Porphyrius ferociously attacked Christianity in his now lost book "*Κατὰ Χριστιανῶν*," where he reviewed —among other texts— *Daniel*, considered by the Christians to be a genuine prophecy, and concluded eventually that it was an *ex eventu* prophecy, a "fraud", written under Antiochus IV in the context of this king's persecution of the Jewish religion.

The most interesting point for us in Porphyrius' comments on *Daniel* is the information, twice mentioned, that two years after the king had defiled the Temple, Seleucid officials placed in it a statue of Zeus Olympius and one or more statues of the king.¹⁶⁷ The text presents some problems. In the first occurrence, Jerome, following perhaps Porphyrius' wording, used two different words: *simulacrum* for Zeus' statue and *statua(e)* for the royal ones.¹⁶⁸ Although both mean "statue," they are usually employed in different contexts. *Simulacrum* is used for the cultic statues of the gods, and *statua* for human representations.¹⁶⁹ Jerome and Porphyry could mean that non-cultic statues of Antiochus were placed in the Temple. The problem is that in the second occurrence, *simulacrum* is also used for the royal statue.¹⁷⁰

How should one evaluate this information? Both Jerome and Porphyry, our earliest evidence,¹⁷¹ wrote many centuries after the events.¹⁷² There is a mention of εἰδῶλα and εἰδῶλεῖα in 1 Macc. 1.43 and 47,¹⁷³ but not in the context of the Temple. If any cultic statues, especially royal ones, had been placed in the Temple, there must have been some mention of them. However, there is no mention, not even where one would expect it the most: in the description of the purification of the Temple.¹⁷⁴ Obviously, Porphyry's "*Κατὰ Χριστιανῶν*" is a polemical text, not a historical treatise.¹⁷⁵ Sometimes, Porphyry follows *Daniel* so blindly, without any criticism, that he also mentions a third Egyptian expedition of Antiochus, which obviously never happened, as this part of *Daniel* is a real prophecy!¹⁷⁶ Moreover, probably, Porphyry's information about the statues of Zeus and Antiochus is his attempt to explain the "abomination of desolation," an attempt in which he failed too.¹⁷⁷

It remains to see what the Greek and Latin authors tell us about Antiochus and his alleged self-deification. Most of them are biased and give a negative image of the king. Among them, the most important is Polybius

¹⁶⁴ Bunge 1973, 179 and 181. On the contrary, in 2 Macc. 5.18–20 the disaster came because of the sins of the Jews themselves.

¹⁶⁵ I study these verses in detail —the attitude of Antiochus IV towards Zeus and Apollo— in another paper, which is in preparation.

¹⁶⁶ As Goldingay 1989, 304 put it, Antiochus IV overreached himself and provoked the distaste of the seer.

¹⁶⁷ Porphyrius FGRL 260 fr.51 and 53 = Stern 1980, 467–470 n.464r vs.3–5 and 12–15, from the commentary of Jerome on 11.31 and 11.36.

¹⁶⁸ Probably, ἄγαλμα and ἀνδριάντες in Porphyrius' text. The discussion of the Latin words concerns the Greek ones as well.

¹⁶⁹ Abel-Starcky 1961, 67; Mittag 2006, 261; Estienne 2009, 257–258.

¹⁷⁰ Interestingly, Jerome reprimanded Porphyry (Stern 1980, 467 n.464r vs.4–5) for suggesting that the abomination of desolation would be the royal statues.

¹⁷¹ Keel 2000, 107 and Doran 2012, 358 n.108.

¹⁷² Scurlock 2000, 131 n.6; Becker 2016, 254–255 clearly doubts the historicity of the information.

¹⁷³ 1.43, "καὶ πολλοὶ ἀπὸ Ἰσραὴλ εὐδόκησαν τῇ λατρείᾳ αὐτοῦ καὶ ἔθυσαν τοῖς εἰδώλοις καὶ ἐβεβήλωσαν τὸ σάββατον" and 1.47, "καὶ οἰκοδομῆσαι βωμοὺς καὶ τεμένη καὶ εἰδῶλεῖα καὶ θθεῖν ὕεια καὶ κτήνη κοινά."

¹⁷⁴ Dancy 1954, 78–80.

¹⁷⁵ I should add two more points concerning Porphyry's evidence: First, we are not completely certain that Jerome read the porphyrian text; probably, he just read Christian refutations of it (Magny 2010, 543–545). Second, since several decades we know that Porphyry did not write a historical work named *Χρονικά* (Croke 1983; Barnes 1994, 55–56; Morlet 2011, 25). Even if it seems certain that he did some historical work for his polemical book *Κατὰ Χριστιανῶν*, he probably was never really interested in the study of the past.

¹⁷⁶ Stern 1980, 468 464r vs.35–37.

¹⁷⁷ Scurlock 2000, 131 n.6; Doran 2012, 358 n.108; Keel 2000, 106–107 (concerning only the statue of Zeus).

owing to his historical quality and professionalism, despite the antipathy he obviously had for Epiphanes.¹⁷⁸ Polybius was a contemporary of Antiochus and probably had first-hand information about the Syrian affairs. He certainly gives valuable information. Diodorus and Livy followed the precious Polybian tradition and somewhat inherited Polybius' bias against Antiochus. On the contrary, Appian had a different, rather positive, opinion on Epiphanes, as he probably ignored the Polybian text. The major problem is that Polybius, Diodorus, and Livius reached us in fragments through later authors, e.g., Athenaeus. Thus, it is not certain that the information ascribed to those authors has always been transferred faithfully. Besides, as we have not in our disposition their whole text, we cannot exclude the possibility that new fragments will appear and show, e.g., that Polybius eventually commented on the king's self-deification. Nevertheless, nothing in the surviving Polybian text concerns this subject.¹⁷⁹

Although silence reigns about Antiochus' deification, there is much information about his behavior, which obviously shocked Polybius and his contemporaries. As we are told, the king used to participate in civic elections in Antioch¹⁸⁰ and to approach the people in a non-royal way.¹⁸¹ Even worse, he used to irrupt in private feasts, shocking the guests, as he was sometimes surrounded by mimes, and even danced naked with them.¹⁸² Finally, in the celebrations at Daphne in 166 BCE, he acted not as a king expected to be the center of the interest but rather as a servant or a magistrate, organizing the parade on a little horse instead of one of royal stature.¹⁸³ Whichever way we interpret these stories, whatever reasons one finds for Antiochus' comportment,¹⁸⁴ it remains difficult to reconcile Antiochus' behavior, as described above, with the intentions of a king who allegedly deified himself.

Certainly, the king had some preferences. Antiochus' preference for Zeus is well-known.¹⁸⁵ There is, nevertheless, some evidence that he could also have been a follower of Dionysus. When he arrived in Rome, the Dionysiac cult was particularly widespread. In 186 BCE, however, a crisis occurred that eventually led to its persecution and a reform.¹⁸⁶ Perhaps, Antiochus knew the cult at that time or, probably, took a taste of it at Athens, an important center of this cult. Maybe, his company of mimes and his nude dances could be explained in the context of Antiochus' participation in Dionysiac rites.¹⁸⁷ If one could prove that Antiochus was active in one god's cult, which probably happened in the case of Zeus, our views concerning his self-deification would probably also change somewhat. Certainly, however, the depiction of the king in *Daniel* 11.36-38 would not stand at all.

¹⁷⁸ No clear reason appears, except the contact as well as the sympathy and friendship that Polybius had with Demetrius in Rome.

¹⁷⁹ Nor does the word game *Epiphanes* / *Epimanes*. Probably, Polybius never saw any coin of Antiochus with the legend ΘΕΟΥ ΕΠΙΦΑΝΟΥΣ. What comment would he have made then?

¹⁸⁰ Pol. 26.1.5 and Diod. 39.35. Antiochus seems imitating Roman magistrates: Feyel-Graslin-Thomé 2014, 18–20 and 24–26, and mostly Bernhardt 2014, 139–141 and 142–145.

¹⁸¹ Pol. 26.1–3; Diod. 29.35; Liv. 41.3. Feyel-Graslin-Thomé 2014, 21–22.

¹⁸² Pol. 26.4 and Ath. 439d.

¹⁸³ Ath. 439b-c, Diod. 29.32.1 and 31.16.2–3. Iossif 2011, 146–150 made an interesting connection between Antiochus and Dionysus. Nonetheless, one should remark that, if Antiochus had really intended to be linked or identified publicly with Dionysus, his attempt was rather a failure, as the brilliant commentator of the festivities, Polybius, did not get the message. Polybius knew that Antiochus died during his Oriental expedition; he would be certainly delighted to make fun of Antiochus' attempt to play Dionysus. The connection between the εὐτελεῖς ἱππάριον and Dionysus' ass is not certain as well. If the king wanted to give this message, he would have. Finally, the appropriation of Dionysus, the god of the defeated Ptolemies, –an idea reminding the analysis of the “Beloved of the ladies” by Bunge 1973– is rather difficult to accept.

¹⁸⁴ Some consider important the influence of the two cities Antiochus lived in, namely Rome (Bernhardt 2014) and Athens (Knoepffler 2014).

¹⁸⁵ Mittag 2006, 139–145.

¹⁸⁶ Liv. 39.8–19.

¹⁸⁷ Already Goukowski 2014, 73ff. See Keel 2000, 114–116 and Scurlock 2000, 143–150 about the *interpretatio graeca* of Yahve as a counterpart of Dionysus rather than of Zeus. Did Antiochus know the sobriquet *Επιμανής* that Demetrius and others in Rome used for him? He –probably an initiate– would secretly smile at this!

4. Conclusion

Mørkholm's monograph of 1966 was a landmark in the studies concerning Antiochus IV. It was, among others, a successful attempt to "clear" Antiochus' image from what centuries of interest and scholarly study had added to it. Antiochus the Hellenizer, the Mad, the Antichrist, etc., were no more an acceptable depiction of the king. Mørkholm and others after him offered us a more realistic image of Antiochus. We recognize now that he was a great politician of the Hellenistic period.

Something was, however, left intact: the belief that Antiochus deified himself. During the nineties, with my few readings at that moment, I was convinced that this could not be true.¹⁸⁸ Above, I asked once again: Was Antiochus IV a self-deified king? Did he actively promote his deification and cult? I tried to show that Bunge's construction that Antiochus promoted his deification to cope with his problems of legitimacy was not so firm, as many believe.

I reviewed the numismatic evidence: Antiochus' rejuvenated portrait, the divine attributes, and the cultic epithets. Interestingly, none of these elements is found on every coin struck under Antiochus IV. I think, this indicates that there was no central, i.e., royal, policy promoting or imposing the king's divinity and cult. Conversely, the literary evidence is not as neat as needed. The Jewish sources, which fed the theories about Antiochus' self-deification, are clearly charged with features coming from the past, from Jewish and Near Eastern ancient literary traditions. On the contrary, the Greek and Latin sources do not even allude to Antiochus' self-deification except for Porphyry, a rather problematic source of evidence. They even destroy Antiochus' image as a king allegedly desiring to be a god; they present him as a very human and rather people-loving king, not as a distant deified monarch.

Nevertheless, the evidence given by many silver and bronze coins is clear. The king is sometimes called Θεός Επιφανής and the royal portrait is occasionally rejuvenated and decorated with stars and rays. Undoubtedly, these coins show a deified king. Is it possible to combine the perplexed numismatic evidence, i.e., the signs of deification that are not uniformly employed throughout the kingdom, with the testimony of the Greek and Latin authors, who were shocked by Antiochus' unkingly behavior?

This may be possible, if we consider that Antiochus' deification was not a royal decision, but a civic action initiated by the local civic elites. Even before Epiphanes, there is evidence that the Seleucids enjoyed civic cults, but the exact date, the circumstances, and their precise nature often elude us.¹⁸⁹ Later, Antiochus IV had an active policy towards the cities. Greek and Latin authors wrote about his actions in Antioch, his capital.¹⁹⁰ Unfortunately, this scattered information focuses mostly on Antiochus' behavior, not on his policy, and leaves us with many questions: Were the mentioned civic offices an innovation of Epiphanes? Was there an evolution to a more "democratic" civic administration during his reign? What degree of autonomy did he allow to the cities? What were his intentions?

Another significant innovation concerning the Seleucid cities was the so-called quasi-municipal and municipal coinages¹⁹¹. Local populations saw the name of their cities, written sometimes in local non-Greek script, on bronze coins. Often, they also saw the images of their local deities on the coins. In addition, Oriental cities were re-founded as Greek ones.¹⁹² Unfortunately, we do not know what this really means, apart from a new name. In the case of Jerusalem, we have some more information, but the problems of interpretation are legion, and the vivid debate on them shows the difficulties involved with approaching this historical phenomenon.¹⁹³ It seems that Antiochus IV started or accelerated a process that led eventually to the poliadization of Oriental cities, whereas, as the coins show, there were probably changes even for Greek cities

¹⁸⁸ Voulgaridis 2000, 82–84. A similar opinion was independently expressed by Dodd 2009, 193–196. We eventually reached similar conclusions following different paths.

¹⁸⁹ OGIS 245.

¹⁹⁰ Mittag 2006, 145–149.

¹⁹¹ On which: Mørkholm 1965 and more recently Hoover 2019 with many interesting new ideas.

¹⁹² Mørkholm 1966, 115–118; Mittag 2006, 201–208.

¹⁹³ The inscription from Toriaion (SEG 47.1745) undoubtedly enlightens somewhat the obscurity we are in.

of the kingdom. Unfortunately, all this is rather elusive. Nevertheless, some decades later, some Seleucid cities apparently had a political life comparable to that in cities of Greece and Asia Minor.¹⁹⁴

Some decades earlier in Asia Minor, several cities promoted actively the cult of Antiochus III as well as of his queen, Laodice. There is no evidence of royal compulsion; on the contrary, the cities took the initiative. We need not to discuss here why they decided to act this way towards their new ruler.¹⁹⁵ There is also no reason to differentiate these newly conquered cities of Asia Minor from those in the Levant and the East. Possibly, the latter did under Antiochus IV what the former had started doing some decades earlier for Antiochus III, *inter alia* in response to royal benefaction. Under Antiochus IV, the great change could have been the evolution of some cities to *poleis* of Greek type with more civic institutions and probably more liberties.¹⁹⁶ Undoubtedly, many honors must have been conferred upon the king; all of them escape us totally. The coins, however, provide some evidence that Antiochus was given divine honors. Probably, these were like those known from so many civic inscriptions from Asia Minor cities under Antiochus III. Under Antiochus IV, some cities also employed the bronze coins they struck in their own names to show their reverence to their king. In fewer cases, even silver coins bore signs of the king's divine status in some cities. In one case, at Ptolemais, from which I started studying the problem of Epiphanes' deification, a special decision was probably taken: to issue coins in the name of the coregent, the future Antiochus V¹⁹⁷. For these coins, the mint of Ptolemais decided to employ not the usual reverse type of Zeus Nikephoros, but the old type, Apollo on the omphalos (Pl.1, 6). What did they have in mind? I cannot help thinking that in the context of a civic cult in honor of Antiochus IV, this king was probably identified with Zeus the king of the gods and, consequently, his son and coregent with Apollo, Zeus' son.¹⁹⁸

Perhaps, we can eventually claim with some certitude that Antiochus Epiphanes did not deify himself and that he did not impose his own cult, supposedly either because of his alleged arrogance or because of his hypothetical need of legitimacy. Instead, it could be a part of the people, the citizens of the Seleucid cities, who decided to honor the king this way.¹⁹⁹ Antiochus was certainly much appreciated by the people. His memory remained alive for years. His son Antiochus V was given the cultic epithet *Εὐπάτωρ*, and his pretended son, Alexander I Balas, took the epithet *Θεοπάτωρ*. Coins in Epiphanes' name were minted posthumously as well. Thus, there is reason to believe that the older views on Antiochus' self-deification should be left behind. The king did not deify himself; the cities gave him divine honors. This would allow us to see his personality as well as his actions under a different light.

¹⁹⁴ I have in mind Ptolemais in Southern Phoenicia towards the end of the Seleucid domination. See Jos. AJ 13.328 and 330.

¹⁹⁵ The encounter of the cities with the immense power of the kings would be always a shock for the cities.

¹⁹⁶ Erskine 2014 suggested there was possibly a link between the development of the ruler cult in the early Hellenistic period and the democracy in the cities. In his concluding words: "*Early Hellenistic ruler cult then is in a curious and somewhat paradoxical relationship with democracy and the polis. It typifies absolutism, yet is the creation of the demos and the ekklesia, the very essence of the polis.*"

¹⁹⁷ SC 1581.

¹⁹⁸ Voulgaridis 2000, 75–85 and Voulgaridis *forthcoming*.

¹⁹⁹ In the context of the Greek kingship and of the Greek colonialism, of course.

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PLATE 1

1. SC 1472b (Numismatic Fine Arts. Auction 18, 31 March 1987, 732).
2. Jean ELSEN & ses Fils s.a. Vente publique 117, 15 juin 2013, lot 62. SC 1476.1d.
3. SC 1542.2 (CSE 2, 1211).
4. SC 1415 (CSE 123).
5. SC 1519 (CSE 2, 375).
6. SC 1581 (CSE 772).

Table 1 Portraits of Antiochus IV (the coins are silver, unless stated differently)		
Mints	Portrait 1	Portrait 2
Antioch on the Orontes	Rather idealized (SC 1395)	Idealized (SC 1394 AV, 1396-7, 1400, 1402-6)
Ptolemais	Realistic (SC 1472-4)	Idealized (SC 1475-6)
Seleucia on the Calycadnus	Rather realistic (SC 1373)	
Soli	Rather realistic (SC 1374-1375)	
Tarsus	Rather realistic (SC 1376)	Idealized (SC 1377-1378)
Seleucia in the Pieria	Realistic (SC 1424)	
Seleucia on the Tigris	Rather realistic (SC 1505)	Rather idealized (SC 1506)
Unc. Mint 80	Rather idealized (SC 1516)	
4drs with draped bust and stars	Rather realistic (SC 1517-8)	
Silver coinage with radiate portrait	Rather realistic (SC 1519-22)	
"Antioch on the Persian Gulf"	Rather realistic (SC 1524)	
Antioch in Persis	Idealized (SC 1526)	
Susa	Idealized (SC 1529-31)	
Ecbatana	Rather realistic (SC 1540, 1542, 1546-1548)	Rather idealized (SC 1539, 1541, 1543-5, 1549)
Mint in N. Media or Hyrcania	Rather realistic (SC 1558-9)	
Unattributed issues	Rather idealized (SC 1561-6, 1568)	

Table 2 Stars and Rays		
Mints	Stars (one or two) AR	Rays AE
Antioch on the Orontes	SC 1396-7, 1400, 1403-4 (two)	SC 1405-6 (AR), 1408-11, 1415 (Eg.), 1416-8 (q-mun.)
Ptolemais	SC 1472 (one), 1473-6 (two)	SC 1479, 1480 (q-mun.)
Perhaps Ptolemais		SC 1483-6
Seleucia in the Pieria	SC 1424 (one)	SC 1425-6 (q-mun.)
Antioch on the Sarus (Adana)		SC 1379-80 (q-mun.)
Hierapolis on the Pyramus		SC 1391 (q-mun.)
Alexandria by Issus		SC 1392-3 (q-mun.)
Hierapolis (Bambyce)		SC 1432-3 (q-mun.)
Perhaps Europus - Dura		SC 1434
Unc. Mint 79		SC 1435-6

Mints	Stars (one or two) AR	Rays AE
Byblos		SC 1442, 1443-7 (q-mun.)
Laodicea in Phoenicia (Berytus)		SC 1448-52 (q-mun.)
Sidon		SC 1453-60 (q-mun.)
Tyre	SC 1463 (one) (AE, q-mun.)	SC 1465 (q-mun.), 1468-9 (q-mun.)
Perhaps Samaria		SC 1489-92
Ascalon		SC 1494-6 (q-mun.)
Antioch on the Callirhoe (Edessa)		SC 1499-1501 (q-mun.)
Antioch in Mygdonia (Nisibis)		SC 1502-4 (q-mun.)
Seleucia on the Tigris		SC 1508-11
Perhaps Seleucia on the Tigris	SC 1513 (one) (AE)	
4drs with draped bust and stars	SC 1517-8 (one)	
Silver coinage with radiate portrait		SC 1519-22 (AR)
Barbarous imitation		SC 1523 (AR)
Susa		SC 1535

Table 3 Cultic Epithets				
Mints	BA	BAΘE	BAΘEN	BAΘ
Antioch on the Orontes	SC 1395, 1402, 1407 (AE)	SC 1396-7, 1403-6, 1408-11 (AE), 1412-5 (AE, Eg. series)	SC 1394 (AV), 1398-1401	
Ptolemais	SC 1472-3, 1477-1479 (AE)		SC 1474-6	
Perhaps Ptolemais	SC 1483-6 (AE)			
Perhaps Europos - Dura		SC 1434 (AE)		
Unc. Mint 79		SC 1435-6 (AE)		
Unc. Western Mint		SC 1437-9 (AE)		
Seleucia on the Tigris	SC 1505-6, 1507-1511 (AE)			
Perhaps Seleucia on the Tigris	SC 1512 (AE)	SC 1513-5 (AE)		
Ecbatana	SC 1540, 1543-6, 1548, 1550, 1551-7 (AE)	SC 1549		SC 1539, 1541-2, 1547 (ΘE)

1

Die A1 from Ptolemais
Realistic portrait
One star
BA

2

From Ptolemais
Idealized portrait
Two stars
BAΘEN

3

From Ecbatana
Realistic portrait
BAΘ

4

From Antioch
Radiated portrait
BAΘE

5

Silver coinage
with radiate portrait

6

Antiochus (V) as coregent
From Ptolemais